

A MACHINE LEARNING MODEL FOR NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM USING HIDDEN MARKOV MODEL.

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ABSTRACT

Cyberattacks are becoming more sophisticated as attackers continuously use diverse strategies and tactics to attack target systems. To avert this impending threat, various possible solutions have been implemented and a variety of security systems keeps emerging. One of these solutions is intrusion detection systems (IDS). The challenge in developing a model that is efficient to detect intrusion is directly dependent on the features selected during the training process and also to detect known and unknown attacks. In this thesis a machine learning model is proposed based on a Hidden Markov Model. The model was trained and tested with data from the NSL KDD dataset, which was selected based on four categories of attacks. The relevant features for training were selected from the dataset based on the scores evaluated from a Laplacian model. New features were extracted from the selected features based on variance from a Principal Component Analysis to decrease the dimensionality of the dataset. K-Means Algorithm was utilized in mapping the extracted data into a new feature space for training. The proposed model produced an accuracy of 83.85% which outperformed the accuracies of the existing models built with the Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Deep Belief Network (DBN), and the Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) which had 71.30%, 74.18%, 71.91% and 80.13% respectively.

Keywords: Cyberattacks, intrusion, security, detection, Hidden Markov Model

1.0 Introduction

The Internet, which has been an insecure pathway for data distribution and communication possess high risk of intrusion and fraudulent activities that include viruses, phishing and cyber-attacks.

Despite the enormous effort put in maximizing internet security today, the internet still records high hacking and system intrusion occurrences. Many measures including real time focus on well-known attacks and threats are taken into consideration daily.

Network, communication and data security in organizations' today have hence become one of the most important aspects in most businesses.

System administrators constantly adopt new information technology techniques to battle this ever-growing anomaly which includes the utilization of cryptography, firewalls and Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS).

Cryptography is the practice of encrypting and decrypting messages into and from secret code/texts [1], and its primary goal is to secure important data in transit as it passes through a medium that may not be secure itself or saved data. This practice provides the following four fundamental security services Confidentiality, Data Integrity, Authentication and Non-repudiation. A firewall monitors and allows/blocks network traffic (i.e. both incoming and outgoing through our systems based on fixed and predefined set of rules). Even though a firewall can prevent some levels of attacks, it cannot fight an attack that is within the organizations network or once the traffic passes through its wall because of its fixed rules nature. This then leads to the introduction of Intrusion Detection Systems which aims at monitoring internal network traffic for suspicious and malicious activities and informs the findings to administrators.

IDS can be categorized into two named; Host Based Intrusion Detection Systems (HIDS) and Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS).

The systems software and/or hardware that is usually located along the network path to check the traffic flow and activities in and out of the network is referred to as the Network Intrusion Detection Systems whilst the Host Based Intrusion Detection Systems are located on the host computer system to monitor the flow of traffic and activities in and out of the host computer [2].

Intrusion detection systems poses a major problem which is analyzing data to determine how legitimate it is or to detect an intrusive activity [3]. Thus, employing data mining techniques is a solution to this data analysis and detection problem [4]. Data Mining is the method of extracting authentic, actionable, and

valid information from large databases. Data mining has two extensive categories namely; Supervised Learning (classification) and Unsupervised Learning (Clustering) [5].

NIDS is aimed at monitoring the traffic within a network for signs of abnormal or malicious activities including attacks on servers and host devices. One benefit of the machine learning techniques includes the advantage in identifying new differences in network traffic - which in most cases signifies malicious activities - by means of training on normal (known good) activities and attacks (known bad) activities. Misuse detections makes comparisons between a user's activities within a system and that of known attacker's signatures that are trying to have infiltrate a system. Although for identifying known intrusion types misuse detection will be ideal, it falls short in detecting new attacks and intrusions. Anomaly detection detects and tracks user activities that deviates from the regular and conventional forms for system users or network. Despite the fact that anomaly detection systems have the capability of identifying unknown attacks, they lag and record large amounts of incorrect alarm rates when usage patterns of system users or the network vary extensively. To identify and detect vulnerabilities more efficiently, signature verification can be mixed with anomaly detection. The greatest difficulty is choosing features that greatly describe the usage patterns of the system or users so that unmalicious activities will not be flagged as intrusions and anomalies thereby reducing the rate of false positives. This paper mainly aims to improve the accuracy of IDS within real time applications of networks and systems by effectively modelling user behavior patterns using relevant features of real time data. IDS seek to detect intrusions, unauthorized and malicious activities on the network, block malicious activities and/or notify the network and systems engineer to take the necessary action in order to prevent the system from further damages.

The formation of DARPA98, KDD99 and NSL-KDD dataset is analogous to an evolutionary process. At each step, faults and deficiencies in the previous dataset were observed and measures were taken to prevent them. On the other hand, CICIDS 2017 is very new and has not been concentrated a lot yet, so it is probably going to contain some minor errors. What these mistakes are and how to fix them is processed in the Data Cleansing section, thus making KDD99 dataset still widely used [6]. This study work will utilize the NSL-KDD for testing and analysis of proposed to reduce the time complexity during runtime.

Data distribution of NSLKDD describes the types of attack found in NSLKDD dataset [6]. The simulated

attacks are grouped into four significant classes as: Denial of service attack, User to root attack, Remote to local and Probe. A DoS is an attack that blocks genuine users from getting entry to required resources by loading excess resources in addition to the resources already available on a system. A U2R attack is an attack where someone with authorized user permissions attempts to obtain root permissions by exploiting the loop holes within software and the operating systems to gain access without approved authorization to the administrator accounts and the host systems. Logging in to a local account or machine to have access to a network using another network or host is an R2L attack. Probe is an attempt that requires scanning a machine or a network in quest of gathering information or finding known vulnerabilities.

2.0 Literature Review

Machine learning algorithms can be classified as stateful or stateless based on the classification method. The HMM can be used in both situations so it can be used for multi-stage intrusion detection and performs a more efficient and effective intrusion detection than other machine learning algorithms [7][8].

Ourston et al. [8] established that HMM performed better than Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Decision Tree (DT) in terms of accuracy with a small dataset even. But the DT performed better the HMM when the training dataset was increased. However, the training time needed was very high.

Lee et al. [7] also proposed an IDS architecture using detection agents that use HMMs.

HMMs were established to be computationally heavy for both training and classification even though they can yield high classification rates [9].

The number of states of an HMM should be known and fixed before the learning process since this cannot be established from the learning algorithm. Lane and Brodley [10] therefore stated that, the performance of HMM and the number of states are directly related. Few states i.e. 1 state many states i.e. 50 and above perform poor.

Ariu et al., [11] also investigated the use of Hidden Markov Models in attack prediction, specifically as applied to HTTP traffic. They found that the HMM algorithm was able to demonstrate better performance than previous attempts by specifically including packet payload in the modeling rather than just trying to make a determination based on packet metadata.

Warrender et al. [12] compared HMM with an enumeration-based algorithm, a frequency-based algorithm and a rule induction technique (RIPPER) [13]. Using a dataset of system calls, HMM

outperformed the other techniques. However, HMM was found to be computationally heavy.

After comparing HMMs with Instance Based Learning (IBL), Lane and Brodley [10] found that HMM produces a much finer precision on identifying intrusions. Subsequently, there wasn't any need in the classification of normal behavior so they put their outcomes with regards to a progressive mix of classifiers, wherein a 'light' classifier, (for example, IBL for this situation) filled in as a channel of increasingly evident data (normal behavior for this situation) at a lower level, at that point at a more elevated level, then moving forward to a much higher level, then to an increasingly far reaching procedure (that is HMM for this situation) was utilized to characterize the rest of the data.

More recent techniques on machine learning applied to intrusion detection have included neural networks [14], Bayesian classifiers [15], support vector machines [16], artificial immune systems [17], and fuzzy logic-based data mining [18].

Ding and Zhai [19] proposed to train an IDS model based on Convolution Neural Networks (CNN), a typical deep learning method, using entire NSL-KDD dataset. Instead of the traditional machine learning used in previous researches, they suggested deep learning has the potential to perform better in extracting features of massive data considering the massive cyber traffic in real life. The model was made up of 3 stacked stages of feature extraction using convolution module which contains a convolution layer followed by a max pooling and no normalization layer. The CNN-based IDS model features had a strong modeling ability for intrusion detection and a higher accuracy as compared with traditional machine learning methods (RF and SVM) and novel deep learning methods (DBN and LSTM).

Kuang et al [20] proposed a multi-layer SVM classifier to estimate whether an action is an attack. KPCA is used as a preprocessor of SVM to reduce the dimension of feature vectors and shorten training time. The experimental results show that the classification accuracies of the proposed KPCA SVM model are superior to those of SVM classifiers whose parameters are randomly selected, and SVM classifier by feature extraction using PCA. Furthermore, the experimental results also show that on intrusion detection data, KPCA perform is better than PCA. The reason lies in the fact that KPCA can explore higher order information of the original inputs than PCA.

Farnaaz and Jabbar [21] used the Random Forest (RF) algorithm to detect the four types of attack, DOS, probe, U2R and R2L in the NSL-KDD dataset. A 10 cross validation was applied for classification. The random forest modelling was compared with j48

classifier in terms of accuracy. Experimental result proved that accuracy for the four types of attacks are increased by using RF. For future work, the researchers proposed evolutionary computation as a feature selection measure to further improve accuracy of the classifier.

Qu et al. [22] used the DBN model to conduct the intrusion detection modeling of communication behavior. They asserted that the DBN model has strong feature extraction ability and classification ability in a large number of high-dimensional data applications. After analysis, DBN-based intrusion detection model performed better classification results than SVM and BP in the detection of NSL-KDD datasets, and the model establishment time is also shorter, which greatly improves the speed of intrusion detection and provides a kind of new research idea.

Naveen [23] proposed an IDS framework that using Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Relevance Vector Machine (RVM) for the data training. The researcher argued that SVM was a binary classifier and ideal for designing IDS but was only capable of identifying intrusions of a particular class thus RVM was proposed to address the limitation. A network feature classification schema and a deterministic feature evaluation procedure was also proposed for identifying the most useful features to be extracted from the network packet upon noting that the performance and scope of detection of IDS was directly dependent on the feature selection stage. Naveen proposed a model applying mathematical, statistical and RVM procedures to place participation of individual features into the detection process. The presented experimental results empirically confirmed that the proposed model can effectively be practical in the mining of new features in the detection process.

Mehmood and Rais [24] applied Naïve bayes, SVM, J.48 decision table and decision tree supervised algorithms for intrusion detection and tested the performance of each on the KDD99 classes of attacks. Each algorithm had different result for each class and none of the algorithms resulted in a high true positive rate with the exception of J.48 decision tree showing a higher accuracy with a low rate of misclassification.

To address challenges in intrusion detection, several methods have been developed using several machine learning algorithms. HMM holds an advantage of being both stateful or stateless based on the classification method therefore can be used for both types of intrusion.

HMM also can yield high classification rates [12][10][9]. Even though HMMs are known to be computationally heavy for both training and

classification depending on the number of states used, the performance and scope of detection was also found to be directly dependent on the feature selection stage so a good feature selection algorithm can greatly reduce the performance complexity [23].

3.0 Methodology

This paper proposes a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) based intrusion detection method that correlate observations in systems (usage patterns and activity profiles) and state transitions to forecast and determine the most feasible intrusion state pattern. HMM is a finite set of states, with each state having an initial probability distribution, state transition probabilities which are the set of probabilities that administer and oversee the frequency of transitions among these states and a probability emission set. The result or observation can be produced in a state depending on the related probability distribution. The final result (outcome) is the only thing evident to the external observer and not the state itself; thus, the name given as Hidden Markov Model [25] The first stage to developing an IDS-based HMM includes analysing and processing traffic on a network into observations that are meaningful which starts by the generation of features from observations, feature selection among those generated features using Laplacian score and new features will be created by combining the generated features using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and mapping this new features to a feature space using K-means algorithm.

3.1 Steps in IDS framework

1. NSLKDD Dataset which has about 41 features is acquired for training and testing
2. A feature selection algorithm (Laplacian score) is employed to select relevant features and also help reduce dimensionality of dataset

Laplacian Score Algorithm

Given the following variables, L_z represent the

Laplacian Score of the z-th feature, f_{zk} denote the k-th sample of the z-th feature, $k = 1, \dots, p$

. The algorithm is state below:

- Construct a graph V having p nodes with an edge between k and w. Each node represents y_k .
- If nodes k and w are not connected, put $S_{kw} = 0$ and $S_{kw} = e^{-\frac{\|y_k - y_w\|^2}{t}}$ if they are connected where t is a suitable constant
- Given L as the Laplacian graph, the z-th feature is given as

$$g_z = [g_{z1}, g_{z2}, \dots, g_{zp}]^T$$

$$\circ E = \text{diag}(S1) \text{ where } 1 = [1, \dots, 1]^T$$

$$L = E - S$$

- The Laplacian Score of the z-th feature is given as follows

$$L_z = \frac{\tilde{g}_z^T L \tilde{g}_z}{\tilde{g}_z^T E \tilde{g}_z}$$

$$\tilde{g} = g_z - \frac{g_z^T E 1}{1^T E 1} 1$$

Where

3. New features are then generated from the selected features using the Principal Component Analysis algorithm to improve training
Principal Component Analysis Algorithm
Input a matrix P with with R rows and c columns (R x c)

- Find the mean vector.

$$\mu = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{i=1}^R p^{(i)}$$

- Construct a mean adjusted matrix.

- Mean value of data points (\tilde{P}) are subtracted from P

- Create the covariance matrix Σ and calculate its the Eigen vectors and values

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{R} \tilde{P}^T \tilde{P}$$

- Pick c' eigen vectors representing the largest eigen values and put them in the columns of $D = [v_1, \dots, v_{c'}]$ as the basis vectors

- Compute each sample as a linear combination of basis vectors.

$$\bullet P' = D^T P$$

4. After applying the PCA procedure to the dataset obtained after the feature selection, the data is mapped into the new feature space using K-means algorithm, using the principal components

K-means algorithm:

- Randomly choose n vectors from the training set X as centroids μ_n .
- For each vector m in the training set, $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$, every vector must belong to a cluster n using the Euclidian distance measure

$$\circ n_m^* = \arg \min_n [d(x_m, \mu_n)]$$

- Recalculate the centroids μ_n by computing the mean of the vectors that belongs to a cluster. This is done for every μ_n . A new centroid μ_n is created if no vector belongs to a centroid by choosing a random vector from x .

5. The HMM model which includes the Veiterbi Algorithm and Baum Welch algorithm is used for training and testing

Viterbi algorithm:

1. Initialization

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Set } r = 2; \\ &\delta_1(j) = \pi_j b_j(o_1), \quad 1 \leq j \leq M \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\psi_1(j) = 0 \quad 1 \leq j \leq M \end{aligned}$$

2. Induction

$$\delta_r(k) = b_k(o_r) \max_{1 \leq j \leq M} \delta_{r-1}(j) a_{jk},$$

$$1 \leq j \leq N$$

$$\psi_r(k) = \arg \max_{1 \leq j \leq M} | \delta_{r-1}(j) a_{jk} |$$

$$1 \leq j \leq N$$

3. Update time

Set $r = r + 1$;
if $r \leq R$; go back to step 2
otherwise continue

4. Termination

$$q_r^* = \arg \max_{1 \leq j \leq M} | \delta_r(j) |$$

$$P(O | \lambda) = \sum_{k=1}^M \pi_k b_k(o_1) \beta_1(k)$$

5. Path backtracking

i. Initialization : Set $r = R - 1$

ii. Backtracking: $q_r^* = \psi_{r+1}(q_{r+1}^*)$

iii. Update time : Set $r = r - 1$; if $r \geq 1$; go back to step b otherwise terminate

Baum-Welch Algorithm

1. Initialization: $B_R(j) = 1, \quad 1 \leq j \leq M$

2. Recursion:

$$\beta_r(j) = \sum_{k=1}^M a_{jk} b_k(o_{r+1}) \beta_{r+1}(k),$$

$$1 \leq j \leq M, 1 \leq r \leq R$$

3. Termination:

$$P(O | \lambda) = \sum_{k=1}^M \pi_k b_k(o_1) \beta_1(k)$$

3.2 Evaluation metrics

For machine learning frameworks, the framework learns from the training dataset, and afterward the general ability of the framework is checked. That is, the performance of the model is analyzed when tested on the testing set of data. The following metrics from the confusion matrix is used.

- True Positive (TP) is a case which represents the fact that both the real value and the predicted value are positive. (e.g., intrusion).
- False Positive (FP) is the instance where the real value is negative (e.g., normal) while the predicted value turns out to be positive.
- True Negative (TN) is the event where both instances turn out to be negative i.e. the real value and predicted value. (e.g., normal).
- False Negative (FN) is situation where the real value turns out to be positive (e.g., intrusion) leaving the predicted value negative.
- Accuracy is the fraction of appropriately classified connections (true positives and true negatives) over the total number of connections in the dataset.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{N}$$

Where N = number of instances.

4.0 Analysis

The NSL-KDD dataset was used for the IDS model. The dataset contains 43 features for each record, with 41 of the features indicating the traffic input itself whilst the last features are labels (regardless of whether it is normal or an attack) and Score (i.e. the severity of the traffic input itself). The dataset contained a total of 77054 normal connections and 71463 attacks. The simulated attacks are classified into four major categories as DOS, U2R, R2L and PROBE. DOS had 9 totally different types of attacks present, PROBE had 6 present, 16 types under R2L categories with 8 U2R attacks types as shown in table 1. The total attacks available comprised of 53383 DOS attacks, 252 U2R attacks, 3751 R2L attacks and 14077 PROBE activities

Table 1: Attacks in dataset.

Attack Category	Attack types	Total attack types
DOS	Apache2, Back, Land, Mailbomb, Neptune, Teardrop, Pod, Smurf, Processtable,	9
PROBE	Satan, Saint, Nmap, Mscan, PortswEEP, IPswEEP	6
U2R	Buffer_overflow, Ps, Httpunnel, Loadmodule, Sqlattack Rootkit, Perl, Xterm	8
R2L	Guess_password, Snpgetattack, Spy, Ftp_write, Imap, Phf, Multihop, Named, Warezmaster, Worm, Xlock, Xsnoop, Sendmail, Snpguess, Udpstorm, Warezclient	16

Figure 2: Number of Instance in Testing Dataset.

The number of records present in the four categories of attacks for both training and testing are shown in figure 1 and figure 2 respectively

Figure 1: Number of Instance in Training Dataset.

For each of the categories of attacks, a model based on Laplacian score was used to rank the relevant features in order of priority for intrusion detection. The Laplacian scores produced are directly dependent on the features relevant for classification of the attacks; i.e. the higher the score the more relevant the feature is for classification. Out of the 41 features available in the dataset the first 10 features according to the Laplacian score were selected to decrease the dimensionality of data as depicted in table 2. Feature extraction was used to further to reduce the dimensionality of the data to reduce the time complexity during runtime for classification. The PCA's main task was used to choose and/or combine the features that preserve majority of the information and eliminate the repetitive components so as to improve the productivity of the ensuing classifiers without degrading their performances. Introduction of some form of threshold is one basic strategy to locate the best subset of transformed component which permit realizing the best classification. For example, variance accounted by a component to be chosen, resulting in choosing principal components, which corresponds to the biggest eigenvalues. The issue with this methodology is that the magnitude of eigenvalue is directly dependent only on data variance and has nothing to do with class information. Nonetheless, measures for choosing the most suitable transformed features are commonly founded on the basis of variance accounted by the features to be chosen [26][27]. Using PCA for extracting the most important components, the ten (10) features derived from the dataset using the Laplacian score are used in the PCA analysis. PCA produced new features (components) from the 10 features. The number of new features (components) generated by the PCA were selected based on the variance. The feature that caused the maximum variance is seen as the first principal component while the feature that is accountable for second highest variance is taken to be the second principal component in that order. The Markov model with

gaussian emission was used to train each attack for prediction. The number of hidden states selected was 6 for each category of attack. The performance with

the model was checked using the accuracy based on the confusion metrics.

Table 2: features selected for each category.

Feature No.	Features	DOS Laplacian Score	PROBE Laplacian Score	R2L Laplacian Score	U2R Laplacian Score
1	duration	0.9989	0.9913	0.6787	0.4712
2	protocol_type	0.9176	0.9645	0.2479	0.5864
3	service	0.9932	0.9761	0.9264	0.5498
4	flag	0.9552	0.9548	0.7313	0.6648
5	src_bytes	0.9988	0.7498	0.3663	0.2819
6	dst_bytes	0.9994	0.3424	0.9396	0.2436
7	land	0.7397	0	0	0
8	wrong_fragment	0.9968	0	0	0
9	urgent	0	0	-0.0007	0.0625
10	hot	0.9946	0.1468	0.9872	0.6041
11	num_failed_logins	0	-0.0001	0.9177	0.1215
12	logged_in	0.9993	0.6551	0.9697	0.873
13	num_compromised	0.9907	0.1076	0.2786	0.22
14	root_shell	0	0	0.5502	0.5718
15	su_attempted	0	0	-0.0002	-0.0029
16	num_root	0	0.1076	0.3417	0.2164
17	num_file_creations	0	-0.0001	0.0703	0.345
18	num_shells	0	0	0.153	0.1957
19	num_access_files	0	0	0.2864	0.1851
20	num_outbound_cmds	0	0	0	0
21	is_host_login	0	0	0.1524	0.2864
22	is_guest_login	0	-0.0001	0.9804	0
23	count	0.9991	0.9994	0.2181	-0.009
24	srv_count	0.9998	0.9937	0.7518	0.3295
25	serror_rate	0.9268	0.7777	0.4094	-0.0068
26	srv_serror_rate	0.9271	0.7829	0.3825	0
27	error_rate	0.899	0.9221	0.6612	0.8821
28	srv_error_rate	0.8989	0.9269	0.6814	0.9254
29	same_srv_rate	0.9943	0.9689	0.2506	0.0695
30	diff_srv_rate	0.7324	0.9153	0.2124	0.1429
31	srv_diff_host_rate	0.684	0.9473	0.042	-0.0048
32	dst_host_count	0.9854	0.9926	0.9837	0.7575
33	dst_host_srv_count	0.9966	0.9942	0.9944	0.34
34	dst_host_same_srv_rate	0.9971	0.9962	0.941	0.7303
35	dst_host_diff_srv_rate	0.7092	0.9418	0.6403	0.3047
36	dst_host_same_src_port_rate	0.9955	0.9128	0.9633	0.7073
37	dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate	0.8658	0.9236	0.697	0.0389
38	dst_host_serror_rate	0.9266	0.7854	0.4439	0.0174
39	dst_host_srv_serror_rate	0.9267	0.7766	0.4858	0.0206
40	dst_host_rerror_rate	0.8925	0.9098	0.7733	-0.0085
41	dst_host_srv_rerror_rate	0.8973	0.9288	0.856	0.8436

The Features for each category were selected based on the scores (i.e. the higher the score the more relevant a feature is) the Laplacian model produced.

The first ten features based on the Laplacian score were selected for each category. From the table 1 it can be observed that the following features were

selected for the DOS category; *srv_count*, *dst_bytes*, *logged_in*, *count*, *duration*, *src_bytes*, *dst_host_same_srv_rate*, *wrong_fragment*, *dst_host_srv_count*, *dst_host_same_src_port_rate* while the features; *count*, *dst_host_same_srv_rate*, *dst_host_srv_count*, *srv_count*, *dst_host_count*, *duration*, *service*, *same_srv_rate*, *protocol_type* and *flag* were selected in order of preference. For the R2L category the following features showed much relevance *dst_host_srv_count*, *hot*, *dst_host_count*, *is_guest_login*, *logged_in*, *dst_host_same_src_port_rate*, *dst_host_same_srv_rate*, *dst_bytes*, *service* and *num_failed_logins*. The features *srv_error_rate*, *error_rate*, *logged_in*, *dst_host_srv_error_rate*, *dst_host_count*, *dst_host_same_srv_rate*, *dst_host_same_src_port_rate*, *flag*, *hot* and *protocol_type* were selected for U2R category based on the scores produced.

higher variance were retained and those with diminishing values were ignored. For each category the number of components chosen varies because of the variance results produced. For the DOS category the first five components were selected from the principal components created because it was observed that the variance of the components diminishes from the sixth component likewise the probe category but for the R2L and U2R, four components and three components were selected respectively. The total variance value for DOS, PROBE, R2L and U2R were 99.09%, 98.93%, 99.92% and 99.46% respectively indicating that majority of the information was preserved and the repetitive components were eliminated. This therefore reduced the dimensionality of features selected and improved the productivity of ensuing classifiers. The table 3 illustrates the various components and their respective variance percent.

Using the PCA the most important components were extracted based on the variance. Components with

Table 3: features selected for each category.

Component No.	DOS Variance%	PROBE Variance%	R2L Variance%	U2R Variance %
PCA1	66.02	52.41	57.94	95.65
PCA2	22.68	19.40	31.30	2.49
PCA3	6.91	16.21	9.06	1.34
PCA4	3.57	7.03	1.64	0.24
PCA5	0.52	3.90	0.03	0.15
PCA6	0.22	0.58	0.02	0.07
PCA7	0.02	0.46	0.01	0.03
PCA8	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02
PCA9	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
PCA10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

The Hidden Markov model with gaussian emission was used to train each attack for prediction in each category. The number of hidden states selected was six (6) for each category of attack. The performance with the model was checked using the accuracy based on the confusion metrics. The figures 3, 4, 5 and 6 represent the accuracies the attacks in each category achieved.

Figure 3: Accuracies for DOS Attacks graph.

Figure 4: Accuracies for PROBE Attacks graph.

Figure 5: Accuracies for R2L Attacks graph.

Figure 6: Accuracies for U2R Attacks graph.

The HMM was compared to Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Deep Belief Network (DBN) and Convolution Neural Network (CNN) to assess the performance rate of the model. These models used the same dataset (NSLKDD) for their evaluation. It was observed that the HMM having an average performance rate of 83.85% outperformed the other models as shown in Table 4. RF had an accuracy of 74.18% [21], SVM had 71.30% [20], DBN had 71.91% [22] and CNN had 80.13% [19].

Table 4: Comparative Analysis.

Model	Overall Accuracy(%)
HMM	83.85%
RF	74.18%
SVM	71.30%
DBN	71.91%
CNN	80.13%

5.0 Conclusion

Developing successful attack detection is to identify the best possible approach which is an extremely difficult task. Several factors were found to influence significantly the outcomes which includes the number of hidden states and feature selection. The studies of feature selection evaluation showed that each category of attack had a unique combinations of feature subset that gave optimal performance.

Also, this thesis showed that it is conceivable to model attacks in a network with models that comprise of small finite number of states. These models can be utilized for both attack detection and attack classification.

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